

ACADEMIC RESILIENCE AND ACADEMIC OUTPUT OF STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Various elements have different effect on the performance of the students, and academic resilience is from one of them. The purpose of current study is to examine "Academic Resilience and Academic Output of Students". In this research quantitative method and survey research design was used. The population of research was all undergraduate student of University of Mianwali. The sample was selected through convenient sampling technique. The sample of current research was two department from faculty of social science (Education, Psychology) and two department from faculty of arts and humanities (Urdu, English). An adapted instrument of Academic Resilience Scale was used in the current research. The instruments reliability was calculated by using Cronbach's alpha and result revealed that the instrument was highly reliable. Data was analyzed by descriptive statistics (Mean and Standard Deviation) and inferential statistics (correlation and t test). There was insignificant relationship was observed between academic resilience and CGPA. There was insignificant gender difference in academic resilience and academic output of students found. It was recommended on the basis of the results that universities need to conduct informational seminars and workshops to spread awareness about academic resilience in students. This awareness may improve their mental well-being as well as their academic achievement of the students.

Key words: Academic resilience, students, academic output, academic performance.

INTRODUCTION

The ability of students to cope academic setbacks, anxiety, and study pressures is known as academic resilience. Students in today's educational environments have many difficulties in both the classroom and society at large. These difficulties could result in higher stress levels and a rise in dropout rates if proper interventions are not implemented. Masten (2001) defines resilience as the capacity to face, defeat, or bounce back from significant risks, particularly academic ones. Therefore, schools, colleges, and universities have a crucial role in helping students develop resilience in order to

secure their academic success and general well-being.

Rapid advancements have been made in a number of fields in the twenty-first century, including politics, industry, education and technology. Traditional learning environments are now more dynamic systems as a result of these modifications. However, poverty, a lack of emotional support, political violence, pandemics, natural disasters and inadequate parental support are only a few of the many risks to the development of children and adolescents around the world. These elements

could have a profound impact on people's lives, families and communities. A worldwide, integrated science of resilience that is backed by evidence-based research is becoming more and more necessary in the face of such challenges in order to influence national and international policy frameworks. This discussion centers on academic resilience, more especially, students' capacity to maintain their academic success and well-being in the face of adversity.

A key component of psychological strength is resilience, which allows people to endure adversity without giving in to stress. According to psychologists, resilient people are better at overcoming misfortune because they have a greater ability to rebuild their life after hardship (Richardson et al., 1990). Resilience is demonstrated in academic contexts when students continue to achieve well in spite of challenging circumstances. According to Mallick and Kaur (2016), for example, students that exhibit resilience continue to perform well academically even in the face of adversity. In a similar manner, Alva (1991) emphasizes that resilient students continue to perform well even after being exposed to stressful situations that usually raise the likelihood of failure or dropping out of school.

The determinants and consequences of academic resilience have drawn more attention in recent decades, making resilience a central topic in psychology and educational research. According to current theories, protective factors are key elements that affect resilience. There are two types of protective factors: internal and external. Social supports and opportunities found in households, schools, peer groups, and communities are examples of external protective factors. Careful connections, high standards, and chances to engage in worthwhile activities are common ways that these supports show up (Ruiz, 2002). Conversely, internal protective variables include personal attributes including self-efficacy, empathy, problem-solving abilities, and self-awareness (Constantine et al., 1999). When combined, these protective factors shield adolescents from unfavorable circumstances and promote flexible social and academic results.

The idea of academic resilience and goal orientation theory have a lot in common. According to research, students' resilience is

impacted by their motivational orientations, whether they are performance- or mastery-oriented. Students who prioritize learning and growth and are mastery-oriented are more likely to show resilience and persevere despite challenges (Dweck, 1986; Sideridis & Kaplan, 2011). Performance-oriented kids, on the other hand, tend to shy away from difficulties and stop trying when faced with difficulties. However, some research suggests that performance goals may increase perseverance following achievement, so they are not necessarily bad (Archer, 1994; Sideridis, 2005). These results imply that motivation, coping mechanisms, and environmental factors are all closely related to resilience.

Scholars have proposed a variety of definitions for the idea of resilience, which has been the subject of much controversy. Despite differences, the majority of definitions agree on two essential elements: positive adaptation and adversity (Windle et al., 2011). According to Rutter (2006), resilience explains why some people continue to have comparatively positive psychological outcomes even after being exposed to long-term stresses. Optimism, self-worth, and social support are examples of protective characteristics that moderate the impact of adversity on people (Rutter, 1985; Sarkar & Fletcher, 2013). Research on whether resilience is better understood as a process a dynamic interaction between people and their environments or as a trait a generally fixed set of personal characteristics has evolved as a result of this discovery (Luthar et al., 2000). Resilience as a process emphasizes the impact of contextual elements like culture, family and community.

Educational academics have modified resilience theories to explain academic events because of the contextual aspect of resilience. For example, Kuperminc et al. (2009) established a cultural-ecological transactional framework that emphasizes how sociocultural settings shape resilience. In contrast to Bronfenbrenner's ecological model, which placed more emphasis on indirect cultural influences, Kuperminc and colleagues contend that sociocultural elements have a direct and immediate impact on students' development in collectivist civilizations like those seen in Asia. Students evaluate their chances and problems through

lenses that include cultural beliefs, family expectations, and society opinions of schooling (Sandoval-Hernández & Białowolski, 2016).

In Asian cultures, where gender roles, social stratification, and collectivist traditions have a big impact on students' educational experiences, this culturally based viewpoint is especially pertinent to understanding academic resilience. To sum up, academic resilience is a crucial concept in modern education. It captures how students continue to achieve well in spite of academic stress, disappointments, and larger societal issues. Building resilience becomes essential for both the achievement of individual students and the advancement of society as a whole as educational systems deal with complicated demands influenced by global changes. Researchers and policymakers can create interventions that improve resilience by utilizing psychological, sociocultural, and educational theories. This will encourage academic perseverance, lower dropout rates, and improve the wellbeing of students.

Literature review:

Over the past few decades, resilience research has undergone tremendous change, with a growing emphasis on academic settings. Recent research has stressed the importance of resilience in education, whereas earlier studies focused on psychological resilience in response to stress and trauma. This section examines academic resilience's definition, causes, and effects as well as actual research from a variety of settings. When people continue to achieve positive results in the face of risk or adversity, this phenomenon is commonly referred to as resilience (Rutter, 2006). This is seen in educational settings when pupils succeed academically in spite of obstacles like socioeconomic disadvantage, inadequate school supplies, or personal struggles. According to Windle et al. (2011), adversity and positive adaptation are the two main components of most definitions of resilience. Sarkar and Fletcher (2013) go on to highlight the importance of protective factors and resources in helping people manage stress and sustain healthy growth. These elements could be external, like positive teacher-student connections, or internal, like self-efficacy.

Different methods have been taken in the literature as a result of the conceptualization of resilience as both a trait and a process. According to Rutter (1987), resilience is a relatively consistent personality attribute that improves coping. Positive affect, optimism, and self-worth are protective qualities (Sarkar & Fletcher, 2013). The process perspective, on the other hand, sees resilience as dynamic and context-dependent, influenced by how people engage with their surroundings (Luthar et al., 2000). This method emphasizes the value of social supports including peers, families, and communities while allowing for variation throughout time and situation (Masten, 2001). Because it takes into consideration how resilience is developed in particular institutional and cultural contexts, the process approach has grown in popularity in educational research.

Researchers make a distinction between internal and external protective factors in academic contexts. Peer support, school climate, teacher expectations, and family participation are examples of external protective factors. Ruiz (2002), for example, emphasizes how supportive connections and involvement opportunities promote resilience. Conversely, cognitive and emotional abilities including empathy, communication, problem-solving, and self-efficacy are examples of internal protective factors (Constantine et al., 1999). These characteristics help students control their emotions, stick with assignments, and maintain their academic motivation under pressure. According to empirical data, these protective characteristics work together to promote academic perseverance and enhanced performance (Mallick & Kaur, 2016).

Resilience is also significantly shaped by motivational orientations. According to Ames et al. (1987), students' responses to academic obstacles are influenced by their goal orientations. Perseverance and resilience are higher among mastery-oriented students who are driven by learning and growth (Dweck, 1986). This opinion is supported by research by Sideridis and Kaplan (2011), which demonstrates that mastery-oriented students persevere through failure more than their performance-oriented counterparts. The situation is complicated, though, by research by

Sideridis (2005) and Archer (1994), which indicates that performance goals, especially when combined with mastery orientations, might occasionally encourage adaptive behavior. As a result, resilience encompasses more than just perseverance; it also entails the flexible integration of many motivational techniques.

Empirical research also emphasizes how resilience varies depending on the situation. As an illustration of how resilience lessens the effects of stressors, Alva (1991) found that academically resilient students in underprivileged environments frequently perform better than expected. Resilient students were more likely to finish their study effectively in spite of emotional or financial difficulties, according to Radhamani and Kalaivani (2021). Fortune et al. (2005) found that resilience and intrinsic drive were related, and that students who pursued mastery-oriented goals were more satisfied and performed better academically. These results demonstrate that resilience is a multifaceted concept impacted by contextual, societal, and individual factors.

There has also been discussion on how resilience should be measured. Three elements adversity, positive adaptation, and protective factors should be evaluated in order to gauge resilience, according to Sarkar and Fletcher (2013). This three-part approach makes sure that resilience is particularly associated with overcoming obstacles rather than being confused with overall well-being. According to Windle et al. (2011), conceptual differences have an impact on the validity of measurements, especially when resilience is viewed as a fixed characteristic. Researchers can more accurately depict resilience as a dynamic phenomenon influenced by contextual and developmental factors by using a process-based measuring technique.

Scholarly interest in the function of cultural environment in resilience has grown significantly. The ecological-transactional model developed by Bronfenbrenner in 1979 highlighted the impact of various systems on development, ranging from societal structures to individual traits. Kuperminc et al. (2009) expanded on this by introducing the cultural-ecological transactional perspective, which

recognizes that cultural influences influence resilience more directly in collectivist societies. For example, students' resilience is significantly impacted by ideals pertaining to gender roles, family responsibilities, and the societal significance of education. According to Sandoval-Hernández and Białowolski (2016), children use cultural "lenses" to understand opportunities and difficulties, which shapes their success strategies. Given the emphasis on interdependence and group objectives in Asian contexts, this viewpoint is especially helpful in comprehending academic resilience.

The literature emphasizes that academic resilience is a complex concept that is influenced by intrinsic traits, external supports, motivational orientations, and cultural contexts. Despite differences in conceptual frameworks and definitions, resilience is generally understood to entail constructive adaptation in the face of hardship. To improve resilience, educators and politicians can create interventions by identifying protective variables and comprehending how they interact. Fostering positive teacher-student connections, supporting mastery-oriented objectives, and advocating for culturally appropriate teaching methods are a few examples.

To sum up, the increasing amount of research emphasizes how critical academic resilience is in predicting student success. Despite contextual hurdles, resilient adolescents are more equipped to overcome hardship, maintain motivation, and accomplish academic goals. To support evidence-based treatments that improve resilience across educational systems, future research must keep improving the conceptualization and assessment of resilience, especially in culturally varied environments.

Methodology

The current study adopted correlational research design and quantitative study type. Population of the current study was all undergraduate students of the University of Mianwali. Multiple sampling technique was used in current study. At first stage University of Mianwali was selected randomly. At second stage the Faculty of Social Sciences and Faculty of Arts and Humanities were selected conveniently. At third stage four departments i.e., Department of Education, Department of

Psychology, Department of Urdu and Department of Islamic Studies was selected faculties conveniently. At last stage students from 2nd, 4th, 6th and 8th semester's students were selected conveniently. The total sample comprised of 380 students. An adopted Academic resilience scale by Cassidy (2016) which contains 30 statement was used in current study. Instruments were presented to the four experts from the field of Education and Psychology. After the finalization of the

instrument by experts opinion the pilot testing was conducted for calculating reliability on the 50 respondents. The reliability statistics showed that instrument was reliable as Cronbach's alpha value was .751. Data was collected by using both means physical and online. Mean, standard deviation, correlation and t test analysis was performed by SPSS V.27. All ethical guidelines were properly followed according to local standards.

Results

Table 1. Level of academic resilience among students (N= 380)

Statements	Mean	Std.D	levels
1. Not accept the teacher feedback.	2.13	1.171	Low
2. Use of feedback to improve my work.	4.02	.972	High
3. Give up.	2.54	1.210	Low
4. Use of the situation to motivate myself.	3.97	.945	High
5. Change in my career plans.	3.24	1.146	Low
6. Get annoyed.	2.96	1.094	Low
7. My chances of success at university were poor.	2.76	1.229	Low
8. I would see the situation as a challenge.	3.69	.989	High
9. Stop thinking negative thoughts.	3.90	1.082	High
10. See the situation as temporary.	3.56	1.067	Medium
11. Work harder.	3.87	.985	High
12. Get depressed.	3.13	1.151	Low
13. Think of new solutions.	3.76	1.048	High
14. Very disappointed.	2.62	1.101	Low
15. Blame the teacher.	2.29	1.230	Low
16. Keep trying.	3.78	.947	High
17. Not change my long-term goals and ambitions.	3.53	1.161	Medium
18. Past successes help to motivate myself.	3.86	1.046	High
19. Think my chances of getting the job I want were poor.	3.06	1.191	Low
20. Monitor and evaluate my achievements and effort.	3.75	.981	High
21. Seek help from my teacher.	3.87	1.033	High
22. Give myself encouragement.	3.78	1.073	High
23. Stop myself from panicking.	3.42	1.119	Medium
24. Try different ways to study.	3.77	1.116	High
25. I would set my own goals for achievement.	3.95	.991	High
26. I would seek encouragement from my family and friends.	3.79	1.088	High
27. I would try to think more about my strengths and weaknesses to help me work better.	3.83	1.025	High
28. I would feel like everything was ruined and was going wrong.	2.87	1.177	Low
29. I would start to self-impose rewards and punishments depending on my performance.	3.29	1.024	Medium
30. I would look forward to showing that I can improve my grades.	4.01	.962	high

Table 1 present high level of academic resilience among students.

Table 2. Relationship between academic resilience and academic output of students (N= 380)

		Academic Output
Academic Resilience	Pearson Correlation	.045
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.378

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 2 represents the correlation between academic resilience and academic output of the respondents. The value of $p = .378$ and $r = .045$ showed an insignificant relationship between academic resilience and academic output. The alternate hypothesis was rejected in current study.

Table 3. Difference in academic resilience in female and male

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. D	Std. E	t	p
Academic Resilience	Female	218	102.839	10.828	.733	-.303	.790
	Male	160	103.181	10.827	.856	-.303	

.05 as a significance level)

Table 3 showed that the value of p is above $.790 < 0.05$, the alternative hypothesis was rejected. It was revealed that there is an insignificant difference between the academic resilience of male and female students.

Table 4. Difference in academic output in female and male

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. D	Std. E	t	p
Academic Output	Female	218	3.3502	.31714	.02148	2.478	.979
	Male	160	3.2673	.32677	.02583	2.467	

Table 4 showed that the value of p is above $.979 < 0.05$, the alternative hypothesis was rejected. It was revealed that there is an insignificant difference between the academic output of male and female students.

Discussion

The main goal of current study was to examine the academic resilience and academic output of students. The current study showed an insignificant relationship between academic resilience and academic output. Zuill (2016) investigated how resilience and academic achievement were related in teenagers enrolled in public schools in Bermuda. Resiliency and GPA and resiliency and arithmetic achievement were found to be statistically insignificantly related, which contradicts the previous research. Sarwar et al. (2010) looked at the minor correlation between Gujranwala, Pakistani secondary school pupils' academic performance and resilience, and they supported recent findings. Academic resilience scores and cumulative grade point averages among undergraduate pharmacy students were found to be negatively correlated in another study (Abubakar et al., 2021). JOWKAR et al. (2013) found a favorable and substantial association between high school students' academic achievement and their academic resilience.

An insignificant difference of academic resilience in male and female was

found in current study. Cecilia and Anthony (2017) looked into how academic achievement and resilience differed by gender among Kenyan secondary school pupils. The results of this study demonstrated that academic resilience varies by gender. It was discovered that the girls were more resilient in the classroom than the boys. Santhosh (2017) disagreed with the current study because the findings of the independent sample t test indicated a significant difference in academic resilience between males and females. The current study was corroborated by Rao and Krishnamurthy's (2018) study on urban public schools in North Bangalore, which found no discernible differences between boys and females in terms of resilience traits or academic aptitude. In pharmacy students, female students scored significantly higher on academic resilience than male students (Abubakar et al., 2021). JOWKAR et al. (2013) found no significant differences in academic resilience between girls and boys, while Mallick and Kaur (2016) found that boys scored higher on academic resilience than girls, which contradicted the current study. Sarwar et al.

(2010) examined the relationship between academic achievement and resilience in secondary level students in Gujranwala, Pakistan, and found that female students are more resilient than male students.

The gender difference in academic output of the students were also insignificant. The study of Matthews et al. (2009) was in favor of the current study and revealed an insignificant gender difference in kindergarten students. The findings of JOWKAR et al. (2013)'s t-test analysis supported the findings of the present study and revealed no discernible differences in academic achievement between boys and females. According to Mwihia (2020) research, Kinangop Sub County students' academic achievement differed significantly by gender; this study was not in favor of current study. another study of Parajuli and Thapa (2017), was also not in favor of current study and revealed a significant gender difference in academic achievement among students

Conclusions

The main goal of current study was to examine the academic resilience and academic output of students. The current study showed an insignificant relationship between academic resilience and academic output. An insignificant difference of academic resilience in male and female was found. The gender difference in academic output of the students were also insignificant.

Recommendations

Following recommendations were made on the basis of the results:

1. Universities need to conduct seminars and workshops to promote awareness about the academic resilience among students, so that it may improve their mental health as well as academic achievement.
2. Future researchers may study other variables along with academic resilience such as academic motivation, social competence etc.
3. The current study used quantitative research design but future researchers may use mix method research for better understandings
4. A bigger and more varied sample from several universities and faculties should be

taken into account by future investigations. Stratified random sampling is one example of a probability sampling strategy that may improve the generalizability of findings.

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